

POLICY BRIEF

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

INTERAGENCY OPERATION IN THE AMAZON FIRE FIGHTING

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POLICY STATEMENT

In recent years, the National Institute for Space Research, INPE, has indicated an increase in fire and deforestation areas in the Amazon region. The indicators show a constant need to develop public control measures and policies in illegal activities and establish a network of agencies to combat these activities. INPE maps fire spots and deforested areas for information from control institutions and the Brazilian government to implement conditions to combat environmental crimes and resolve impacts on the environment and the local population. The Brazilian government's control and combat proposals are made through two sequential inter-agency operations involving civilian agencies and the armed forces: Verde-Brasil Operation and Verde-Brasil Operation 2. These deliberations through interagency action are emergency forms of managing the environmental crisis that has involved the Amazon region and the Brazilian response to the international context.

BACKGROUND

Biodiversity in the Amazon region is significant and must be protected as a world heritage site. The Amazon is a large reserve of fauna and flora that has the potential for scientific research and the therapeutic area's development. In the region, we find the riverside population and indigenous peoples that inhabit the reserves. All this wealth has long been the target of predatory hunting with animal trafficking, degradation, and exploitation of illegal wood, significant deforestation, illegal mining. These are some of the challenges that the Brazilian government has to maintain the protected area.

To integrate the Amazon region with national development and protect the area, the Brazilian government created the Legal Amazon concept. The area of the Legal Amazon is about 5,217,423 km², corresponding to 61% of the national territory and comprising 9 Brazilian states: Acre, Amapá, Amazonas, Mato Grosso, Pará, Rondônia, Roraima and Tocantins and part of the state of Maranhão. INPE carries out the control of these areas through a calculation methodology that verifies the rate of deforestation in the region, thus establishing political guidance for decision-makers to implement actions to control and combat illegal actions in the Legal Amazon. INPE uses satellite images that are interpreted by georeferencing, classified, and categorized in a database.

As a measure to control and combat illicit activities and fires in the Amazon region, the Brazilian government, through an interagency operation under the control of the Ministry of Defense and with the participation of other ministries, carried out in the last two years (2019 and 2020) the Verde-Brasil Operations. With the Armed Forces and civil agencies' participation such as Federal Police, IBAMA, Civil Police, Military Police, Firemen, among other bodies, the actions of an interagency character presented expressive results in the fight against environmental crimes.

FINDINGS

The importance of interagency work with an environmental focus has increased dialogue and partnerships among ministries and institutions. Verde Brasil Operation, started in 2019, was an interagency operation coordinated by the Ministry of Defense and carried out cooperatively with public security, border, intelligence, and environmental agencies. Presidential Decree authorized operation No. 10,022 / 2019 to settle and control outbreaks of fire in addition to combating environmental crimes. Verde Brasil Operation's main results had a direct impact on the reduction of the fire and on the arrest and criminal records that culminated in 120 arrests, in the confiscation of 200 illegal vehicles that served for the illegal removal of wood, in fines and seizures. These figures demonstrate that the operation carried out in a cooperative and coordinated manner had an immediate and emergent effect in the established crisis in the Amazon region when the Brazilian government then implemented the interagency model as a fast and efficient way of sharing information, resources, and actions—assigned to each of the agencies involved.

The operation mobilized military and civilian contingent, divided the geographical space into three joint commands (Joint Command of the Amazon, Joint Command of the North, and Joint Command of the West), and had logistical support for illegal seizure of wood and fire fighting the land, naval and air patrol. The development of these actions was beneficial for combating illegal activities and protecting Amazonian biodiversity.

However, interagency operations are carried out on an emergency basis in the Amazon region, is characterized by the non-permanent nature of the actions. As trafficking in wood and animals, among other illicit acts such as deforestation and fires caused by illegal nature, are not quickly resolved, in 2020, the Brazilian government relaunched Verde Brasil Operation 2, characterizing a need for further work between the agencies.

Verde Brasil Operation 2 began in May 2020 with a balance in June of approximately 934 fines imposed, 116 arrest warrants in the act, seizure of illegal vehicles and boats, seizure of drugs. With the intensification of activities in the second Operation Green Brazil, the result in fines increased by 15% from the previous operation, and the number of institutions that cooperated also increased, highlighting FUNAI, ICMBio, ABIN, INCRA, in addition to the institutions that also did part of Operation Green Brazil in 2019.

CONCLUSIONS

The development of the Amazon region and environmental protection against fires and illegal deforestation has been combated efficiently through interagency cooperation. The decision-making model based on the institutions involved' strategic and tactical-operational capacity has revealed great potential in emergency crises, being, therefore, responsive to the existing challenges. The speed of the process, the governance model, based on interagency cooperation, the sharing of information, the delegation of tasks according to each agency's competence, the division of resources, and actions have shown great success in protecting Amazon.

SUGGESTIONS

Studies on interagency cooperation have revealed a significant gain in the proximity of these relationships, one of which is establishing greater trust between different agents in emergencies. This study has a significant challenge in establishing models or patterns of cooperation, coordination, and network among institutions that can provide the best way to act in interagency environments at the strategic and operational levels. In interagency operations, the scarcity of material, human and financial resources is often circumvented by a greater exchange among institutions with more significant conditions and preparedness, even though the competence to act is not hers.

Verde Brasil Operation, used as a case study to verify the positive impact of an environmental nature's interagency cooperation, favors theoretical studies and brings us closer to practical verifying actions as a constant learning process. However, operations like these, of a temporary nature, also have temporary efficiency of more significant impact while they are in operation. The demand for combating illegal activities, in this case those involving the environmental issue of fires and deforestation in the Amazon region, is to establish long-term planning, in an inter-agency way, with constant training and qualification among the agents and that reveal a greater understanding of the interagency environment, the consensual and cooperative decision-making process, the encouragement of proactive behavior, the building of trust and the implementation of a secure intelligence and information sharing system.

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